

BB-4312: ORGANIZATIONAL DEVELOPMENT AND CHANGE

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Abstract

This paper explains the reason I took the module which is Organizational Development and Change. It is the study of organizational development and change combined with the influence of Brunei's national culture and Universiti Brunei Darussalam's (UBD) organizational culture shapes career perspectives in business administration. The module teaches students leadership skills to handle problems fairly and benefits others. Making sure every decision is made aligns with the organizational goals. UBD's cooperative learning environment enables the student to have collaborative problem-solving so that they are prepared to work in a diverse workplace. This ensures the future career is not only towards personal goals but also organizational success and positive impact.

Main Text

As a student that is planning to take business administration as a major, I take organizational development and change because this module can teach me how to become an effective leader that can guide teams. It can build confidence to lead and support transformation in any business setting with confidence. This module can help to understand how to diagnose problems, reduce resistance and align strategies with the organizational goals. Identifying the root cause of the problems and finding an effective solution that ensures the change supports the long-term success and growth of the company.

In Brunei's national culture, they deeply teach us in values of respect, harmony and a community which significantly shaped the way I view my future career. These shape my perspective on teamwork and decision making. Making sure that the work I do will also benefit others, for example giving back to the community. It builds professional ambition for more career growth and leadership positions to treat employees fairly and respectfully.

As for Universiti Brunei Darussalam (UBD) organizational culture, helps to develop my academic and professional outlook. They provide cooperative learning, inclusivity and adaptability which prepare me to thrive in diverse and dynamic workplaces. UBD's teaching style emphasizes critical thinking or problem solving that usually involves group projects, discussions rather than just individual work. This teaching style can shape my future career by collaborating effectively and listening to different viewpoints is the kind of teamwork that is expected in the modern workplace. The world is also changing quickly, for example globalization, with the UBD's teaching technique can make us become more comfortable with the change.

In conclusion, both Brunei's national culture and UBD's organizational culture have played a vital role in shaping my career perspective. It teaches us to face challenges such as rapid change with resilience and making sure the decision making is fairly treated that also benefit others. These

influences ensure that my future career will not only focus on personal growth and leadership but also contribute positively to society and organizational success.